

**MUSIC, ARTS, PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND HEALTH (MAPEH)
TEACHERS' TECHNOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL, AND
CONTENT-KNOWLEDGE (TPACK): BASIS FOR
INTERVENTION PROGRAM**

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Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) Teachers' Technological, Pedagogical, and Content-Knowledge (TPACK): Basis for Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of Technological, Pedagogical, And Content Knowledge (TPACK) practices among MAPEH teachers to describe the teacher utilization of technology, pedagogies, and content knowledge for school year 2023-2024 which led to the development of a proposed intervention program for MAPEH teachers. The research utilized a purposive sampling technique in getting the sample population among the different schools in the Division of Pasig City. This study utilized a non-experimental, quantitative research design. As regards the level of TPACK of MAPEH Teachers the School Administrators and MAPEH teachers themselves perceive that there is a small difference between the mean score of MAPEH teachers in the three areas as supported by the mean scores of 3.40 and School administrators with a grand mean score of 3.39 only and indicated no significant difference on the respondents' perceptions. In addition, there is No Significant Difference on the perceptions of the School Administrators and MAPEH Teachers as regards the challenges encountered by the MAPEH Teachers. Furthermore, there is No Significant Difference on their perceptions and the challenges experienced by the MAPEH Teachers. Lastly, it was found out that there is significant relationship between TPACK Competencies as to Content Knowledge and the Encountered Challenges Encountered. Based on the results of the study, The MAPEH Teachers' Intervention Program was crafted to enhance the TPACK to a very high level.

Keywords: *TPACK, MAPEH teachers, intervention program*

Introduction

Integrating technology into education is crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 4: Quality Education. The SDGs provide a framework for global development efforts, aiming to address various social, economic, and environmental challenges by 2030.

Through the revolutionary process of technology integration in education, students may now access high-quality educational information, anywhere at any time, by using digital tools and resources like educational applications and online platforms, which closes the access gaps in education. This enhances learning results overall while also empowering individual learners. Technology integration ensures that every learner has the chance to succeed academically and get ready for a better future by adapting teaching strategies to the varied requirements of students, these creates a more inclusive and equitable learning environment.

There are many factors that affect the teachers' performance to the delivery of the lessons, it includes utilization of technology, use of accurate pedagogies in the classroom, and updating the content knowledge of the teacher in teaching the subject matter. TPACK is an instructional model that includes the successful integration and educators' expertise in technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. Asad et al. (2021) recognized that each component of the TPACK has a role in the model and further elaborated that students' comprehension knowledge of the subject (CK) with effective combination of virtual reality tools and services (TK), instructional comprehension of how and why learning occurs, what students learn, mindsets and behaviors could help the teachers achieve superior teaching inside a virtual reality environment.

Teachers acknowledged the need for professional development when utilizing digital technologies. Older professionals may exhibit weak skills in using digital tools in teaching (Hämäläinen et al., 2021). Teachers should also improve their skills in lesson delivery or teaching strategies to entice students to learn more about their lesson. Effective teaching strategy supports independent learning thus, creating an avenue for students to explore and advance their understanding of the lesson while addressing problems involving distractions and limited attention span that derail their learning experiences and hinder class participation.

The impact of TPCK in the different categories of in-service teachers also identifies the relationships of the teachers' preference on the manner of utilizing the TPACK framework in the teaching process. Systemic planning and consultation are necessary to develop an effective TPACK program for teachers.

The aforementioned factors present an obvious challenge among teachers, especially to those teachers who are teaching different content in one subject areas like the MAPEH teachers. Grounding on exploration by Baker et al., (2020) in the Swedish didaktik of physical education tradition, what they uncover was that when teachers adopt the 'athletic-looking teacher as a healthy role model' mindset, they tend to focus on specific health ideals, use teaching methods, and work toward a specific educational goal. This involves giving importance to maintaining a healthy weight, ensuring physical functionality, placing the teacher at the heart of the educational process. This aims to shape students into healthy individuals through sports participation.

Teachers teaching MAPEH or Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health are offered in junior high school. This integrative approach

requires teachers to give lessons on different competencies thus, making it challenging for them to accomplish. To assist MAPEH teachers on their professional developmental needs the following research problems will be presented.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of TPACK practices of MAPEH teachers and its challenges to describe the teacher's utilization of technology, pedagogies, and content knowledge for school year 2023-2024. Results were utilized to create an invention program for MAPEH teachers. More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of TPACK of MAPEH teachers as perceived by the school administrators and MAPEH teachers themselves in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. Technological Knowledge
 - 1.2. Pedagogical Knowledge
 - 1.3. Content Knowledge
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the School Administrators and MAPEH teachers as regards the level of TPACK of the MAPEH teachers themselves in term of the abovementioned criteria?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the MAPEH Teachers in TPACK as perceived by the School Administrators and MAPEH teachers themselves?
 - 3.1. Technological utilization
 - 3.2. Teaching strategies
 - 3.3. Classroom management
 - 3.4. Trainings/seminars attended
 - 3.5. Mastery of the subject matter
4. Is there a significant difference between the level of competencies and challenges experienced by the MAPEH teachers as perceived by the School Administrators and MAPEH teachers themselves?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceptions of the MAPEH Teachers and School administrators as regards the level of competencies on TPACK and the challenges encountered by the MAPEH themselves?
6. What intervention program may be proposed based on the results of the study?

Literature Review

The Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework describes the integration of technology within teaching and the interaction of the three main bodies of knowledge: technological knowledge, content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge. Niess et al. (2020) explained that in this approach, technology in teaching is characterized as something well beyond isolated knowledge of specific software or hardware, rather technology that was introduced into teaching context that presented new concepts and demands connections between all three components.

Good teaching can only be attributed to technology if it requires a shift in existing pedagogical and content domains. This means that teachers with develop TPACK, using technology to plan and design learning experiences with interest-specific pedagogies created for desired content and necessary for the specific learning context (Meda, 2023). In alignment with Pathurohman et al. (2023), the TPACK framework incorporates several essential elements critical for successful teaching in today's educational environment.

To understand the TPACK framework it is fundamental to acknowledge the roles of each component as well as their interaction with each other. With the K-12 curriculum, various changes and adjustments were made by teachers to meet the requirements for senior and junior high school teachers. This change in curriculum affects teachers' pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, and technological knowledge (Garcia & Martinez, 2023).

Samonte, K. & De Guzman, P. (2019) emphasized the importance of providing the ICT training among MAPEH teachers to improve the technological skills as the 21st century undergoes rapid transformations with the emergence of new technologies, there is a growing demand for MAPEH teachers to possess robust pedagogical competencies, content mastery, and the ability to skillfully integrate technology into teaching for the enrichment of students' learning experiences.

On the other hand, Buedron, N. (2019) identifies that the knowledge and skills of non-MAPEH major teachers teaching physical education is low, as identified by the head teacher and students. Thus, a professional development program for non-MAPEH major teachers should be implemented to address the identified weakness.

Similarly, Ramos et al., (2020) also examines the technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK) confidence level of pre-service teachers in selected Philippine teacher education institutions. Their findings show that pre-service teachers are confident in the learning experiences provided by the Teacher Education Institutions. They frequently demonstrate acceptable teacher competency and standards, using these experiences. Furthermore, the levels of TPACK confidence of the secondary and elementary pre-service teachers significantly differ from each other, with the former being more confident with their learning experience and practices.

Meanwhile, in Calang, J. (2021) research centers on how literacy teachers initially understand critical pedagogy and how a special

training program can help them develop better ways to teach literature. In simpler terms, the latter study is all about looking at how MAPEH teachers become better at their TPACK level, while Calang et al.'s research focuses on how literacy teachers teach literature in a special way. Regarding to teaching methods, the latter study might be looking at different ways MAPEH teachers can teach using technology and other skills, while Calang, J. (2021) research is more about how teachers think about teaching literature critically.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design specifically the non-experimental design. Since the study uses quantitative data to interpret the results of the research study. A survey questionnaire from Mishra et al. (2023) was adapted and modified to fit the demand of the current research study. The TPACK survey questionnaire was used to create a proposed professional development program for MAPEH teachers teaching physical education.

Respondents

The respondents consist of ninety-one (91) MAPEH teachers ranging from teacher I to teacher III, fifteen (15) master teachers ranging from master teacher I and master teacher II and five (5) department heads from five (5) different schools in the Division of Pasig City. The participants answer survey questionnaires.

Instrument

The experts' validation tool was developed and adopted from the works of Oducado (2020). It is composed of 13 questions that measures the relevance, appropriateness, clarity, consistency, and acceptability of the survey questionnaire.

The MAPEH Teachers' TPACK survey instrument was constructed to self-assess the MAPEH teachers TPACK competencies. It is composed of two main parts; Part I includes the MAPEH teachers' TPACK Survey questionnaires and MAPEH teachers challenges in teaching the subject area. The survey questions it includes pedagogical knowledge (PK), Technological Knowledge (TK), and Content knowledge (CK): 6 TK items, 12 CK items, and 7 PK items.

These survey questionnaires were administered to determine the school administrator's perception towards the TPACK competencies needed by MAPEH teachers to effectively deliver the MAPEH subjects to the students by the teachers in the most efficient manner. Similar validation tool was used to evaluate the survey questionnaire.

Procedure

The researcher secured an endorsement from the graduate school Dean and thesis adviser of Marikina Polytechnic College to conduct the study. Second, the researcher submitted an official letter to the school's division superintendent to secure a permit to conduct the study. Upon the release of permission to carry out the study, the researcher encoded the validated survey questionnaire in Google Forms and tested surveys. The researcher then sent an official letter to the school's head of school or principals. After which, it was forwarded to the respondent's email address, and the respondents themselves filled out a few test questionnaires. Data was gathered from the platform and some test questionnaires were personally administered to the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

This study established ethical measures for the confidentiality of the information acquired from all the informants. It imposed neutrality with no manipulation of answers, and all responses were treated with the utmost confidentiality. Likewise, the privacy of the identities of the informants was sustained.

Results and Discussion

TPACK level of MAPEH Teachers as Perceived by the School Administrators and MAPEH Teachers Themselves

Table 7. Respondents' Perceptions on the TPACK level of MAPEH Teachers regarding Technology Knowledge

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The teacher knows how to solve his/her technical problems.	3.38	HK	3.30	HK
2. The teacher can learn technology easily.	3.40	HK	3.45	HK
3. The teacher keeps up with important new technologies.	3.49	HK	3.55	VK
4. The teacher frequently plays around the technology.	3.23	HK	3.10	HK
5. The teacher knows about a lot of different technologies.	3.08	HK	3.35	HK
6. The teacher has the technical skills needed to use technology.	3.25	HK	3.35	HK
Overall Weighted Mean	3.31	HK	3.35	HK
Standard Deviation	0.54		0.49	

Overall, MAPEH teachers yielded a weighted mean of 3.31, with the Standard Deviation of 0.54, while administrators have a weighted mean of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 0.49. These findings suggests that both the school administrators and MAPEH teachers possess a high-level Technological Knowledge. However, this also implies the need for MAPEH Teachers to improve their technological knowledge. Samonte & De Guzman (2019) recommended the importance of providing ICT training among MAPEH teachers to enhance their technological skills.

Table 2. Respondents' Perceptions on the Level of TPACK of MAPEH Teachers regarding Pedagogical Knowledge

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The teacher knows how to assess student performance in a classroom.	3.65	VK	3.65	VK
2. The teacher can adapt the teaching based-upon what students currently understand or do not understand.	3.62	VK	3.55	VK
3. The teacher can adapt the teaching style to different learners.	3.55	VK	3.35	HK
4. The teacher can assess student learning in multiple ways.	3.59	VK	3.45	HK
5. The teacher can use a wide range of teaching approaches in a classroom setting.	3.54	VK	3.50	VK
6. The teacher is familiar with common student understandings and misconceptions.	3.49	HK	3.30	HK
7. The teacher knows how to organize and maintain classroom management.	3.69	VK	3.40	HK
Overall Weighted Mean	3.59	VK	3.46	HK
Standard Deviation	0.44		0.55	

School administrators strongly agree on MAPEH teachers' ability to assess' students, with a mean of 3.65, adapt teaching styles based on students' need with a mean of 3.55, and implement teaching approaches with a mean of 3.50. Despite these differences of responses between the two groups their overall weighted mean is relatively similar. MAPEH teachers' general weighted mean is 3.59 with a standard deviation of 0.44, while School Administrators general weighted mean is 3.46 with a standard deviation of 0.55.

The discrepancy in the responses of the two groups regarding teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge is address by Mercado et al. (2020). He capitalized that in pedagogy, participants agreed that TPACK allows experiential learning experiences and promotes problem solving skills. This data implied by the researcher that to strengthen the pedagogical knowledge of the MAPEH teachers that will meet the standards of the school administrators.

Table 3. Respondents' Perceptions on the Level of TPACK of MAPEH Teachers regarding Content Knowledge

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
Music	3.01	HK	3.08	HK
1. The teacher has sufficient knowledge about music.	2.96	HK	3.00	HK
2. The teacher can use a musical way of thinking.	2.99	HK	3.15	HK
3. The teacher has various ways and strategies for developing my understanding of music.	3.08	HK	3.10	HK
Arts	3.24	HK	3.28	HK
4. The teacher has sufficient knowledge about the arts.	3.21	HK	3.20	HK
5. The teacher can use an artistic way of thinking.	3.26	HK	3.35	HK
6. The teacher has various ways and strategies of developing my understanding of arts.	3.26	HK	3.30	HK
Physical Education	3.51	VK	3.57	VK
7. The teacher has sufficient knowledge about physical education.	3.45	HK	3.60	VK
8. The teacher can use a physical education way of thinking.	3.58	VK	3.50	VK
9. The teacher has various ways and strategies for developing my understanding of physical education.	3.51	VK	3.60	VK
Health	3.49	HK	3.55	VK
10. The teacher has sufficient knowledge about health.	3.40	HK	3.55	VK
11. The teacher can use a healthy way of thinking.	3.55	VK	3.55	VK
12. The teacher has various ways and strategies for developing my understanding of health.	3.52	VK	3.55	VK
Overall Weighted Mean	3.31	HK	3.37	HK
Standard Deviation	0.36		0.44	

Teachers possessing the best subject matter expertise and proficiently utilizing technology to improve learning, educators can expand learners' comprehension, and cultivate analytical and problem-solving abilities.

This provides educators the cornerstone upon which to build meaningful and pedagogically sound technological integrations to enhance student learning and achievement.

Similarly, Ramos et al (2020) points out the importance of conceptual knowledge to the subject matter and the use of TPACK framework provides opportunity to deliver a real-life experience among the in-service teachers and to the students.

Significant Difference Between the Perception of School Administrators and MAPEH Teachers Themselves in Their Level of TPACK

Table 4. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of TPACK of MAPEH Teachers as to Technology Knowledge*

Respondents	n	OWM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	3.31	0.54	0.34	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	3.35	0.49				

Apparent from the table, the computed t value of 0.34 is less than the critical t value of 1.98. At a 5% significance level, this indicates that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Consequently, there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents on the level of TPACK of MAPEH teachers regarding technology knowledge.

This implies that the perception of the two groups of respondents does not differ from each other, their observations, practices, and tangible evidence such as classroom observations and narratives support this claim. Therefore, the utilization of technology in the classroom is very evident from the practices of the MAPEH teachers as well as from the perception of the school administrators.

Table 5. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of TPACK of MAPEH Teachers as to Pedagogical Knowledge*

Respondents	n	OWM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	3.59	0.44	1.17	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	3.46	0.55				

Based on the table, the computed t value of 1.17 is lower than the critical t value of 1.98. This leads to the conclusion that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at a 5% significance level. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents on the level of TPACK of MAPEH teachers regarding Pedagogical Knowledge.

This implies that both groups of respondents have a common understanding about the pedagogical knowledge of MAPEH teachers. This understanding is based on the practices, observations and other documents that support this claim. It also shows how much pedagogical knowledge of MAPEH teachers was viewed by school administrators and provides a basis for future training on new pedagogies.

Table 6. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of TPACK of MAPEH Teachers as to Content Knowledge*

Respondents	n	OWM	S	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	3.31	0.36	0.63	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	3.37	0.44				

The table demonstrates that the computed t value of 0.63 is below the critical t value of 1.98. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained at a 5% level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents on the level of TPACK among MAPEH teachers regarding Content Knowledge.

This implies similarities between the perception of MAPEH teachers and school administrators regarding content knowledge. The content knowledge of MAPEH teachers comprises four areas, music, arts, physical education, and health education, even though the test of significance suggests a no significant difference, researchers should investigate the competence of MAPEH teachers in teaching music and arts compared to physical education and health education.

This is necessary since the weighted mean for music and arts subject is much lower than for physical education and health education.

Experiences and Challenges Encountered by MAPEH Teachers as Perceived by School Administrators and MAPEH Teachers Themselves

The table 7 indicates that the main problem encountered by MAPEH teachers is a weak internet connection, hindering the productivity of teachers to bring effective teaching and learning experiences towards their students. On the other hand, school administrators perceived that selecting the right technology of applications that are aligned with pedagogies and content knowledge presents a challenge to MAPEH teachers.

In relation to the research conducted by Anud, E. M., & Virgencita, B. (2023), TPACK involves the active participation of science educators, and their responses underwent descriptive-correlational and causal comparative techniques.

Table 7. Respondents' Perceptions on the Experiences and Challenges Encountered by MAPEH Teachers Regarding Technological Utilization

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The teacher doesn't feel left behind when it deals with the use and implementation of technology in the classroom	3.04	A	2.70	A
2. The teacher needs to learn new skills in using new technology and web applications.	2.91	A	3.05	A
3. The teacher's school/workplace has strong and available internet connections.	2.44	D	2.45	D
4. The teacher doesn't have difficulty in choosing the suitable technology or application that are aligned with his/her pedagogies and content-knowledge.	2.81	A	2.45	D
5. The teacher can easily organize the scores/data of his/her students' output to make the recording easy.	2.98	A	3.25	A
Overall Weighted Mean	2.84	A	2.78	A
Standard Deviation	0.43		0.37	

Table 8. Respondents' Perceptions on the Experiences and Challenges Encountered by MAPEH Teachers Regarding Teaching Strategies

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It is easy for the teacher to create meaningful task by integrating technology to their teaching methodology.	3.10	A	3.45	A
2. It is easy for the teacher to motivate the students in the classroom discussion using technology.	3.26	A	3.55	SA
3. The teacher can always apply new teaching strategies with the use of technology.	3.22	A	3.35	A
4. The students can utilize technology in exposing and presenting their product in the classroom.	3.21	A	3.35	A
5. The teacher can use new technology and suited strategies in maintaining the interest of the students during the class discussion.	3.27	A	3.40	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.21	A	3.42	A
Standard Deviation	0.64		0.52	

School administrators strongly believe that the use of technology is an effective tool to motivate learners to study hard, as evidenced by the mean score of 3.55. Additionally, it indicates that the utilization of technology positively impacts on the teaching pedagogies, creativity, and the development of learning materials to enhance the students' learning experiences. Thus, there was no direct problem encountered by MAPEH teachers regarding the use of pedagogical knowledge.

Table 9. Respondents' Perceptions on the Experiences and Challenges/Problems Encountered by MAPEH Teachers regarding Classroom Management

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. There is an increase in classroom participation as the teacher integrate new web applications to his/her teaching strategies.	3.29	A	3.20	A
2. There is an increase in the student achievement as the teacher integrate technology to the teaching methodologies.	3.20	A	3.35	A
3. The students became more efficient in submitting their output in classroom using digital platforms.	3.17	A	3.50	SA
4. The students are excited with the new lesson because of the use of technology in the classroom.	3.33	A	3.30	A
5. The teacher can make different approaches in classroom management using different technology.	3.27	A	3.25	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.25	A	3.32	A
Standard Deviation	0.65		0.51	

School administrators perceived that MAPEH teachers effectively utilized the digital platforms for submitting student outputs. This approach not only minimizes expenses of students in creating portfolios but also enhances the efficiency of document submission to teachers, as indicated by the mean scores of 3.50.

Overall, classroom management does not pose a significant problem for teachers, with mean scores of 3.25 for MAPEH teachers and 3.32 for school administrators.

Table 10. Respondents' Perceptions on the Experiences and Challenges/Problems Encountered by MAPEH Teachers Regarding Trainings/Seminars Attended

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. There is sufficient seminars/ workshops provided to MAPEH teachers on the use of new technology in the classroom.	2.69	A	2.80	A
2. There is sufficient seminars/workshops provided to MAPEH teachers in improving the teachers' teaching strategies.	2.70	A	2.80	A
3. There is a sufficient seminars/ workshops that harness the teachers' understanding in music.	2.57	A	2.75	A
4. There is a sufficient seminars/ workshops that harness the teachers' understanding in Arts.	2.63	A	2.95	A
5. There is a sufficient seminars/ workshops that harness the teachers' understanding in Physical education.	2.82	A	3.10	A
Overall Weighted Mean	2.68	A	2.88	A
Standard Deviation	0.67		0.58	

Both MAPEH teachers and school administrators agree on the importance of providing seminars and training for MAPEH teachers. This is crucial to determine if there is an inefficiency of the provisions of these services to the MAPEH teachers.

The overall weighted mean suggests that there is enough support in terms of training and seminars; however, the level of agreement is relatively low.

Table 11. Respondents' Perceptions on the Experiences and Challenges/Problems Encountered by MAPEH Teachers regarding Mastery of the Subject Matter

	Respondents			
	MAPEH Teachers		School Administrators	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The teacher demonstrates a high level of proficiency in the subject matter.	3.27	A	3.10	A
2. The teacher can explain the content of the topic clearly.	3.32	A	3.10	A
3. The teacher mastered knowledge about the theories and principles related to the subject matter.	3.28	A	3.10	A
4. The teacher can explain the importance and usefulness of the subject matter in the real world	3.36	A	3.10	A
5. The teacher can relate the information to one another.	3.30	A	3.10	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.31	A	3.10	A
Standard Deviation	0.67		0.72	

Although the table above shows a unanimous agreement about the mastery of MAPEH teachers and School administrators, their weighted mean scores differ. MAPEH teachers mean is 3.31 while school administrators mean is 3.10.

The lower mean indicates a deeper understanding of the seminars and the training needs that are more aligned with their requirements in teaching music, arts, physical education, and health.

Significant Difference Between the Level of Challenges Encountered by School Administrators and MAPEH Teachers Themselves

Table 12. Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Challenges/Problems Encountered in terms of Technological Utilization

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	2.84	0.43	0.56	1.98	Fail to reject the Ho	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	2.78	0.37				

Consequently, there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents regarding the level of challenges encountered with respect to technological utilization.

This suggest that both MAPEH teachers and school administrators agree on with the current conditions of the technological utilization among the MAPEH teachers. Which affect the quality of the teaching and learning process of the students and teachers.

Table 13. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Challenges/Problems Encountered in terms of Teaching Strategies*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	3.21	0.64	1.38	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	3.42	0.52				

As a result, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% level of significance. This supports the notion that there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents regarding the level of challenges encountered with respect to Teaching Strategies. This implies that teaching strategies is properly observed by the school administrators, and that they are aware of the conditions of their teachers' conditions and welfare.

Table 14. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Challenges/Problems Encountered in terms of Classroom Management*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	3.25	0.65	0.45	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	3.32	0.51				

Consequently, at a 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is to retain the null hypothesis. This affirms that there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents regarding the level of challenges encountered with respect to Classroom Management.

Table 15. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Challenges/Problems Encountered in terms of Trainings/Seminars Attended*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	2.68	0.67	1.22	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	2.88	0.58				

At a 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents on the level of challenges encountered with respect to Trainings/Seminars Attended.

Table 16. *Test of Difference in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Challenges/Problems Encountered in terms of Trainings/Seminars Attended*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
MAPEH Teachers	91	3.31	0.67	1.24	1.98	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
School Administrators	20	3.10	0.72				

Consequently, there is no significant difference in the perception between the two groups of respondents regarding the challenges faced in Mastery of the Subject Matter. This implies that both groups understand the needs and requirements of MAPEH teachers for a strong mastery of the subject matter.

Significant Relationship Between the Competencies and Challenges Encountered by School Administrators and MAPEH Teachers Themselves

Table 17. *Test of Relationship Between the Competencies in terms of Technology Knowledge and Challenges/Problems Encountered*

Variables	Pearson r	Strength	Computed t Value	Critical t Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Technological Utilization	0.28	Weak	3.13	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Teaching Strategies	0.20	Very low	2.19	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Classroom Management	0.23	Weak	2.53	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Trainings/ Seminars attended	0.03	Very low	0.32	1.98	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Mastery of the Subject Matter	0.28	Weak	3.13	1.98	Reject the H ₀	Significant

At a 5% significance level, this implies that the null hypothesis should be rejected, providing evidence that there is a significant relationship between the Competencies and Technology Knowledge, and the Challenges Encountered in terms of Technological Utilization, Teaching Strategies, Classroom Management, and Mastery of the Subject Matter.

Despite the positive correlations of technological knowledge with the aforementioned factors, it might also pose a concern for technological disruptions if not regulated by policies and standards. This is clearly mentioned by Mhlanga (2022) that investigates the

educational paradigms and theories that guide the education sector toward a successful transition to industry 4.0.

Table 18. *Test of Relationship Between the Competencies in terms of Pedagogical Knowledge and Challenges/ Problems Encountered*

Variables	Pearson <i>r</i>	Strength	Computed <i>t</i> Value	Critical <i>t</i> Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Technological Utilization	0.16	Very low	1.74	1.98	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Teaching Strategies	0.18	Very low	1.96	1.98	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Classroom Management	0.16	Very low	1.74	1.98	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Trainings/ Seminars attended	0.04	Very low	0.43	1.98	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Mastery of the Subject Matter	0.30	Weak	3.37	1.98	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

Pedagogical knowledge exhibits positive relationships with the issues and concerns regarding the mastery of the subject matter of MAPEH teachers. Hence, there is a need for more opportunities for teachers to be trained by experts in the pedagogical and conceptual understanding of the subject matter. This observation was also cited by Shah (2022), who pointed out the specific training needs of in-service language teaching faculty in higher education, thereby contributing to the development of tailored and effective professional development programs.

Table 19. *Test of Relationship Between the Competencies in terms of Content Knowledge and Challenges/ Problems Encountered*

Variables	Pearson <i>r</i>	Strength	Computed <i>t</i> Value	Critical <i>t</i> Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Technological Utilization	0.23	Weak	2.53	1.98	Reject	0.23
b. Teaching Strategies	the H ₀	Significant				the H ₀
c. Classroom Management	0.27	Weak	3.01	1.98	Reject	0.27
d. Trainings/ Seminars attended	the H ₀	Significant				the H ₀
e. Mastery of the Subject Matter	0.24	Weak	2.65	1.98	Reject	0.24

These findings imply that there is a positive relationship between the content knowledge of the teachers and the issues and concerns regarding technological utilization, teaching strategies, classroom management and mastery of the subject matter. It is important to address the issues and concerns of teachers, hence a different perspective should be considered to develop a good professional development program. As mentioned by Niess, M. L., Gillow-Wiles, H., & Angeli, C. (2020), emphasis should be place on unveiling the longitudinal and multidimensional development of knowledge that teachers possess.

The Proposed Intervention Program

Rationale

The results of the study reveal an intriguing insight: Both school administrators and MAPEH teachers recognize the depth of knowledge possessed by MAPEH educators on their Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK). This mutual recognition provides a strong foundation for enhancing instructional strategies in MAPEH.

The alignment between school leaders and MAPEH teachers is particularly promising, indicating a shared understanding of the educational landscape, as evidenced by them on TPACK knowledge and the challenges faced by MAPEH teachers.

This unity bodes well for future collaborative efforts. However, despite their outstanding level of experience, both groups express as shared belief in continuous improvement. This notion lays a groundwork in an intervention program aimed at refining existing practices rather than fixing what is perceived as broken. The focus is on enabling the MAPEH curriculum, encompassing music, arts, physical education, and health education.

The study underscores the importance of proactive measures to enhance TPACK among MAPEH teachers. By doing so, teachers can leverage technology and pedagogical tools effectively to deliver meaningful learning experiences for students in the MAPEH curriculum. Implementing a targeted intervention program can facilitate this process, empowering MAPEH teachers to excel in their roles.

Objectives

This proposed intervention program would be a whole year activity, which aims to achieve the following:

Enhance teachers' comprehension of fundamental concepts in their fields, such as music elements, aesthetics, art history, performance techniques, sports, diet, and mental health. This information will help with the efficient incorporation of technology into instructional methods.

Equip teachers with proficiency in using a variety of technology tools relevant to their subject areas, such as digital audio workstations, graphic design software, fitness tracking apps, and virtual simulations.

Provide educators insightful and helpful criticism on the following: establishing relevant assessments, integrating performance tasks,

and setting priority standards.

Encourage teachers to explore innovative pedagogical approaches that leverage technology to enhance student engagement, facilitate learning, and promote creative expression, skill development, and health behavior change.

Empower teachers to integrate technology seamlessly into their instructional practices, balancing pedagogical considerations, content expertise, and technological affordances to create authentic learning experiences for students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

That, both the school administrators and MAPEH teachers agreed that the level of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge of MAPEH Teachers have similarities in their responses which seem to show that the school administrators have direct involvement on the welfare of the MAPEH teachers. That, the latter are aware of the teachers' strengths and weaknesses which they use as basis to develop and create professional development programs.

That, both the school administrators and MAPEH teachers agreed that the MAPEH teachers themselves experienced and encountered different challenges in the fields of technological utilization, teaching strategies, classroom management, training or seminars attended and mastery of the subject matter.

That, the MAPEH teachers' pedagogical knowledge is directly influenced by the challenges they encounter in their mastery of the subject matter and vice versa.

That, the School Administrators and the MAPEH Teachers have the same observation on the level of TPACK Competencies and the challenges experienced by the MAPEH Teachers themselves.

That, the encountered challenges of the MAPEH Teachers are somehow associated with their Technological Knowledge, Pedagogical Knowledge and Content Knowledge.

A proposed intervention program was crafted to enhance the TPACK of MAPEH teachers to a very high level.

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